

In Search of Music's Volkston – Ideology, Computer Science and the History of Musical Form

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Figure 1:

Music Example 7:

Two staves of musical notation in 4/4 time. The first staff has a bracket labeled 'I' over the first four measures and a bracket labeled 'II' over the last four measures. The second staff has a bracket labeled 'III' under the last four measures. Colored bars are placed below the notes: orange bars under the first four measures of both staves, and red bars under the last four measures of both staves.

Figure 3:

Figure 4:

Figure 7:

<i>e e f g g f e d c c d e e d d</i>	<i>e e f g g f e d c c d e d c c</i>
<i>e</i> - 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0	1 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0
<i>e</i> - - 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0	1 2 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0
<i>f</i> - - - 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0	0 0 3 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
<i>g</i> - - - - 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0	0 0 0 4 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
<i>g</i> - - - - - 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0	0 0 0 1 5 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
<i>f</i> - - - - - - 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0	0 0 1 0 0 6 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
<i>e</i> - - - - - - - 0 0 0 1 0 0 0	1 1 0 0 0 0 7 0 0 0 1 0 0 0
<i>d</i> - - - - - - - - 0 1 0 0 0 0	0 0 0 0 0 0 8 0 0 1 0 0 0 0
<i>c</i> - - - - - - - - - 1 0 0 0 0	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 9 1 0 0 0 0 0
<i>c</i> - - - - - - - - - - 0 0 0 0 0	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 10 0 0 0 0
<i>d</i> - - - - - - - - - - - 0 0 0 0	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 11 0 0 0
<i>e</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - 0 0 0	1 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 12 0 0
<i>e</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - 0 0	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
<i>d</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - 0	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
<i>d</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
<i>e</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	- 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0
<i>e</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	- - 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0
<i>f</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	- - - 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
<i>g</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	- - - - 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
<i>g</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	- - - - - 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
<i>f</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	- - - - - - 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
<i>e</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	- - - - - - - 0 0 0 1 0 0 0
<i>d</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	- - - - - - - - 0 1 0 0 0 0
<i>c</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	- - - - - - - - - 1 0 0 0 0
<i>c</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	- - - - - - - - - - 0 0 0 0
<i>d</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	- - - - - - - - - - - 0 0 0 0
<i>e</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	- - - - - - - - - - - - 0 0 0
<i>d</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	- - - - - - - - - - - - - 0 0
<i>c</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	- - - - - - - - - - - - - - 0
<i>c</i> - - - - - - - - - - - - - - -	- - - - - - - - - - - - - - -

Music Example 9:

Freude schöner Götterfunken

measures: 16
numberOfNotes: 63
upbeat: 0
quarterLength: 64.0

Figure 11:

Figure 12:

Figure 13: Criterion Cr(b1-)

Figure 14: Criterion Cr(b3)

Figure 15: Criterion Cr(bc1-)

Figure 16:

Figure 20:

Figure 22:

Figure 23:

Figure 25:

Figure 27:

Figure 28:

Figure 29:

Figure 30:

Figure 31:

Figure 32:

Figure 33a:

Figure 33b:

Figure 33c:

